

GEOFFREY CHAUCER IS THE GREATEST ENGLISH LITERATURE REPRESENTATIVE

Absamatova Shohida Baxtiyor qizi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8426101>

Introduction. Geoffrey Chaucer lived in England from the late 1340s until his death on October 25, 1400, and he is best remembered for his work on *The Canterbury Tales*. He has been referred to as the "father of English literature" or, alternately, the "father of English poetry". He was the first author to be laid to rest in Westminster Abbey's Poets' Corner, which is now known as such. As a philosopher and astronomer who wrote the academic *A Treatise on the Astrolabe* for his 10-year-old son Lewis, Chaucer also rose to popularity. He continued his public service career as a bureaucrat, courtier, diplomat, and lawmaker.

Key words: *literature, poetry, works, The Canterbury Tales, manuscripts, humoristic devices.*

For Chaucer's writings the subsequent record is clear. His contemporaries praised his artistry, and a school of 15th-century Chaucerians imitated his poetry.

The Book of the Duchess, *The House of Fame*, *The Legend of Good Women*, and *Troilus and Criseyde* are only a few of Chaucer's numerous other works. When Anglo-Norman French and Latin were still the two most common literary languages in England, he is credited with being vital in establishing the legitimacy of the use of Middle English in literature. Thomas Hoccleve, Chaucer's contemporary, praised him as "the firste fyndere of our fair langage" (i.e., the first person able to identify lyrical material in English). The origins of about two thousand English terms can be found in Chaucerian manuscripts.

As an alternative to the alliterative Anglo-Saxon meter, Chaucer wrote in the continental accentual-syllabic metre, which had emerged in English literature by the 12th century. Chaucer is renowned for metrical innovation, having created the rhyme royal. He was also one of the first English poets to employ the five-stress line, a decasyllabic cousin of the iambic pentameter, in his work, with only a few other anonymous short works adopting it prior to him. The organization of these five-stress lines into rhyming couplets, which was originally used in his poem *The Legend of Good Women*, was utilized frequently in his later work and eventually became into one of the English language's most common literary forms. His early influence as a satirist is also significant, as evidenced by the use of the amusing accent and other typical humoristic devices.

Chaucer's poetry, along with that of other authors of the time, is recognized for its role in transforming the Kentish and Midlands dialects of Middle English into the London Dialect. This is most likely exaggerated; the court, chancery, and bureaucracy, of which Chaucer was a member, continue to have a more likely influence on the evolution of Standard English.

Due to the impact of the Great Vowel Shift, which occurred some time after Chaucer's death, modern English is somewhat distinct from the language of his poetry. The present audience finds it challenging to read Chaucer because of the change in English pronunciation, which is still not entirely grasped.

The ending -e's position in Chaucer's verse is unclear, but it's possible that at the time the poet was writing it was becoming less common in spoken English and that its usage was sporadic. It might have been a holdover from the time when most nouns in Old English ended in -e, the

dativ singular. The last -e is sometimes to be vocalized and sometimes to be silent, according to Chaucer's versification, but there is still debate about this. The majority of academics pronounce it as a schwa when it is vocalized.

The majority of the terminology is familiar to readers today, with the exception of the inconsistent spelling. The Oxford English Dictionary lists Chaucer as the first author to utilize a number of common. The numerous poets who reacted to or mimicked Chaucer's poetry testifies to the wide-spread popularity of his works. One of the first poets to finish Chaucer's incomplete Tales was John Lydgate, while Robert Henryson's Testament of Cresseid completes the Cressida story that was left hanging from Troilus and Criseyde. The Romantic era poets' later interpretations of Chaucer's works were influenced by their inability to separate the later "additions" from the genuine Chaucer because many of the copies of Chaucer's works contain material from these poets.

Chaucer was acclaimed for his stories by writers of the 17th and 18th centuries, including John Dryden, but not for his rhythm and rhyme since few critics could read Middle English at the time and because the text had been mangled by printers, producing a sloppy mess.

References:

1. "Geoffrey Chaucer". Cambridge University Press. 2019. Retrieved 20 April 2020.
2. "Chaucer". Cambridge University Press. 2011. Retrieved 20 April 2020.
3. Robert DeMaria, Jr., Heesok Chang, Samantha Zacher, eds, A Companion to British Literature, Volume 2: Early Modern Literature, 1450–1660, John Wiley & Sons, 2013, p. 41.